

Halogen Exchange Reaction in the Preparation of Some Dihalocyclopentadienyl, Methylcyclopentadienyl-Titanium(IV) and Dihalobis(isopropylcyclopentadienyl)-Titanium(IV)

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$(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiF}_2$ has been prepared from $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ by the action of NH_4F in aqueous medium and its halogen exchange reactions with halo acids have been studied in aqueous medium. Exchange reactions of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ with boron trihalides have also been studied in nonaqueous medium. The products of exchange reactions have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight, conductivity, ir and ^1H nmr spectroscopy.

FIRST alkyl-substituted cyclopentadienyltitanium(IV) dihalide reported was $(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ ¹. Sullivan and Little² utilized the reaction of fulvenes with LiAlH_4 , LiC_5H_5 and $\text{Li-}n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$ to produce allylcyclopentadienide salts which were then treated with TiCl_4 to produce bis(substituted-cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride or with CpTiCl_3 ($\text{Cp} = \text{C}_5\text{H}_5$) to produce [(substituted-cyclopentadienyl)(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride. Using this method, a number of dihalo complexes including $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ ³ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ were prepared².

We report here the preparation of $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiF}_2$ by the reaction of NH_4F on $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ in aqueous medium. The exchange reactions of difluoro complex have been studied in aqueous medium with halo acids. The exchange reactions of dichloro complexes of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{Ti(IV)}$ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{Ti(IV)}$ have also been studied in nonaqueous medium with boron trihalides.

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

Dichloro(cyclopentadienyl, methyl cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV), $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$, was prepared by the reaction of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{TiCl}_2$ and $(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti(I)}$ in 1:1 mole ratio in THF ⁴. Dichlorobis(isopropylcyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$, prepared as described by Sullivan and Little².

Boron trifluoride in the form of adduct $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O.BF}_3$ was procured from Alfa-Alfa Chemical Co. Ltd., Germany while BBr_3 and BI_3 were prepared by the reaction of NaBH_4 and Br_2 or I_2 in CH_2Cl_2 ⁵. Organic solvents used were predried and purified.

[A] Preparation of difluorobis(isopropylcyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) : $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (1.6650 g ; 0.005 mole) was heated for 20 min under reflux in 50 cm³ of water containing a little HCl (pH of the solution adjusted to ~ 1.2). To the clear cold solution was added the concentrated aqueous solution of NH_4F (5 cm³ ; 10%). The reaction mixture assumed yellow colour and a yellow precipitate started settling. The reaction mixture was extracted with five 10 cm³ portions of CH_2Cl_2 . The combined extract was dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 and evaporated to ~ 10 cm³ under reduced pressure. On adding petroleum ether (60-80°), yellow $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiF}_2$ was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered and dried *in vacuo* to give >90% yield of the complex.

Exchange reactions of $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiF}_2$ with halo acids in aqueous medium :

[B] Preparation of $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiX}_2$ ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) : $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiF}_2$ (1.0 g) was stirred with 10 cm³ of HCl (35%) at ambient temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$) for 5 min. A suspension was obtained with a marked colour change from yellow to red. The resulting suspension was filtered on sintered glass frit (porosity G-4) and dried on a boiling water bath under suction. The residue on recrystallisation from CHCl_3 yielded red coloured $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ in >90% yield. $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiBr}_2$ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiI}_2$ were prepared in >90% yield by the same method using HBr (47%) and HI (55%), respectively.

Exchange reactions of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ with boron trihalides in non-aqueous medium :

[C] Preparation of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiX}_2$ and $(i\text{-C}_5\text{H}_7\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiX}_2$ ($X = \text{F}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$) : $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ (7.89 g ; 0.03 mole) was refluxed with BF_3 (1.36 g ; 0.02 mole) in 100 cm³ of CH_2Cl_2

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TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA FOR $[(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)]TiX_2$ AND $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiX_2$

Complex*	m.p.°C (colour)	%Found (Calcd.)				M.W. Found (Calcd.)	Ring protons chemical shifts in τ		
		C	H	Halogen	Ti		C_5H_5	$CH_2C_5H_4$	$C_5H_7C_5H_4$
$(Cp, MeC_5H_4)TiF_2$	194 (Yellow)	57.1 (57.39)	4.9 (5.21)	16.4 (16.52)	20.4 (20.87)	208 (230)	3.64	4.0 (m)**	
$(Cp, MeC_5H_4)TiCl_2$	210 (Red)	49.8 (50.18)	4.4 (4.56)	26.6 (26.99)	18.4 (18.25)	280 (263)	3.4	3.6 (m)	
$(Cp, MeC_5H_4)TiBr_2$	174 (Dark red)	37.2 (37.5)	3.17 (3.41)	44.9 (45.45)	13.4 (13.63)	368 (352)	3.34	3.52 (m)	
$(Cp, MeC_5H_4)TiI_2$	200 (Black)	29.2 (29.59)	2.5 (2.69)	56.3 (56.95)	10.6 (10.76)	416 (446)	3.2	3.3 (m)	
$(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiF_2$	143 (Yellow)	63.6 (64.0)	7.0 (7.33)	12.2 (12.66)	16.2 (16.0)	282 (300)	—	—	3.9, 3.65 (m) (m)
$(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiCl_2$	170 (Red)	57.1 (56.65)	6.1 (6.6)	20.9 (21.32)	14.0 (14.41)	355 (333)	—	—	3.6 (m)
$(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiBr_2$	77 (Dark red)	45.1 (45.49)	5.1 (5.21)	37.4 (37.91)	11.0 (11.37)	441 (422)	—	—	3.5 (m)
$(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiI_2$	226 (Black)	36.8 (37.2)	4.1 (4.26)	48.8 (49.22)	9.1 (9.30)	528 (516)	—	—	3.16, 3.0 (m) (m)

* Cp=C₅H₅; ** m=multiplet.

for 0.5 hr. The solvent and BCl₃ formed in the reaction were distilled off on a low heat *in vacuo*. The residue was recrystallized from tetrahydrofuran-petroleum ether (1:1) mixture to give yellow product, $[(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)]TiF_2$ in > 90% yield.

$[(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)]TiX_2$ (X=Br, I) were prepared from $[(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_2$ by the method [C], using appropriate boron trihalides. $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiX_2$ (X=F, Br, I) were also prepared from $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiCl_2$ by the method [C], using appropriate boron trihalides.

Physico-chemical measurements: The ir spectra of the complexes in the region 4000–200 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 621 grating spectrophotometer in KBr/CsBr. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 spectrometer at 30° in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined ebullioscopically in benzene and conductivities were determined in nitrobenzene, using Elico, type CM82T conductivity bridge. Elemental analyses for C and H were done microanalytically and gravimetric procedure was followed for titanium and halogens.

Results and Discussion

Attempts to prepare $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiX_2$ (X=I, Br) by refluxing $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiCl_2$ with KBr or KI as described by Wilkinson and Birmingham⁹ for dihalobis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) were unsuccessful and the products isolated proved to be mixtures of unconverted chloro complex, corresponding bromo or iodo compound and mixed halo compounds (as indicated by the ¹H nmr spectra).

However, both the chlorine atoms of $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiCl_2$ got exchanged quantitatively by the action of NH₄F in aqueous medium. The halogen exchange of $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiF_2$ with HX (X=Cl, Br, I) is also quantitative in aqueous

medium. In nonaqueous medium also $[(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_2$ and $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiCl_2$ exchange their halogens quantitatively with BX₃ (X=F, Br, I). These exchange reactions are simple to carry out and therefore, may be used to prepare halo complexes satisfactorily. An extra advantage in preparing the halo complexes by exchange reaction in nonaqueous medium with boron trihalides is the purity of the products, as the only other reaction product in these reactions in BCl₃ which is completely removed at ambient temperature (~30°) under reduced pressure.

The products of these exchange reactions are coloured and are soluble in CH₂Cl₂, CS₂, C₆H₆, CCl₄, CH₃COCH₃ and THF. These halo complexes are thermally stable and possess sharp melting points. The molecular weights determined in benzene indicate them to be monomers (Table I). The molar conductivity of these complexes (0.5 mM solutions in nitrobenzene) is in the range of 0.18–0.24 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹. This confirms their nonelectrolytic nature.

IR spectra: According to Fritz⁷ pentahaptocyclopentadienyl and methylcyclopentadienyl rings in the ir spectra of $(C_5H_5)(CH_2C_5H_4)TiX_2$ complexes are identified by the appearance of ir active bands at ~3100 cm⁻¹ due to (C–H) stretching (rings), at ~1440, ~1410 cm⁻¹ due to (C–C) in-plane skeletal vibrations, at ~1030, ~1010 cm⁻¹ due to C–H asymmetric in-plane deformation and at ~850, ~820 cm⁻¹ due to (C–H) symmetric out-of-plane deformation. The absorption band due to (C–H) stretching vibrations of methyl group appears at ~2900 cm⁻¹.

The presence of cyclopentadienyl group in the ir spectra of $(i-C_5H_7C_5H_4)_2TiX_2$ complexes is identified by the appearance or ir active bands at ~3100 cm⁻¹ due (C–H) stretching, at ~1435 cm⁻¹ due to (C–C) in-plane skeletal vibrations, at ~1020 cm⁻¹

due to (C-H) asymmetric in-plane deformation and at $\sim 820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to (C-H) symmetric out-of-plane deformation.

¹H NMR spectra : The ¹H nmr spectra of these complexes exhibit two types of resonances, (i) due to ring protons and (ii) due to protons of alkyl part attached to the ring. The ¹H nmr data for ring protons are given in Table 1. The τ values for the -CH₃ protons of CH₃C₅H₄ in the complexes of the type (Cp, MeC₅H₄)TiX₃ are 7.86, 7.65, 7.59 and 7.6 for fluoro, chloro, bromo and iodo complexes, respectively. C₈H₇ protons of C₈H₇C₅H₄ in the complexes of the type (i-C₈H₇C₅H₄)₂TiX₃ exhibit two types of signals. One in the form of a broad multiplet due to -CH protons of i-C₈H₇ group which appears between τ (4.0-6.4), while the other in the form of doublet in the ratio (1 : 1) due to CH₃ protons of i-C₈H₇, appearing between τ (8.67-8.9).

The proton chemical shifts (τ values) for ring protons are sufficiently separated. Moreover, the τ value for the ring protons decreases from fluoro to iodo complex in the order F > Cl > Br > I. This trend is opposite to what is expected from simple

electronegativity criteria. However, it may be interpreted as indicative of an overriding trend in p π -d π bonding in the same sense from halogen to titanium⁸.

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